

Policy Cloud

Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This deliverable compiles the aspects related to the Development of the pilot cases of the PolicyCLOUD project

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ATOS	Atos Spain S.A.
EC	European Commission
E2E	End to End
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
ITA	Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEAs	Law Enforcement and Society
MAG	MAGGIOLI SPA
OKS	OKYS LTD
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PME	Policy Model Editor
RAND	Database of Worldwide Terrorism
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SOF	Municipality of Sofia
UC	Use Case
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Center

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Executive Summary

This document is the final version of the Use Case Scenarios Definition & Design. It provides an updated version of the use case scenarios description, and completes the information presented there. In addition, this deliverable collects the refined versions of the visualization requirements and KPIs per use case. KPIs are classified in three categories: business, technical and scenario related. The modelled policies will be realized / implemented and monitored through the Policy Development Toolkit against these KPIs.

The use cases have been defined taking into account the information collected from the different stakeholders participating in the pilots, as well as from the previous experience and know-how of the project partners. Several workshops have been organized by the project to gather feedback and requirements from relevant stakeholders. This document is the basis for the definition of the main features to be provided by PolicyCLOUD tools and models in the different pilots' implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this deliverable, we review the 3 use cases of the PolicyCLOUD project, focusing on their different scenarios, their KPIs and the visualization requirements. The objective is to present the main indicators to be monitored in the project and show the visualization requirements of the future tools, which are an essential part of the project developments.

1.1 Summary of Changes

This deliverable is an updated version of the deliverable D6.10 [4]. In this new version the following sections have been updated:

- Use case scenarios
- Key actors
- KPIs
- User requirements:
 - Business requirements
 - Visualization requirements
 - Co creation feedback

These sections have been updated according to the evolution of the project and the information gathered in the different workshops carried out by the partners participating in the pilot use cases.

With respect to deliverable D6.10 [4], the description of the scenarios has been improved with the relation with government policies and a description of the user story. KPIs have been restructured into three categories to follow the classification provided in the DoA with the addition of a category related to specific scenario KPIs. Also, the feedback collected from the last co-creation workshops has been referenced in the visualisation requirements, and taken into account for the further adaptation and improvement of the corresponding scenarios.

In the same way, it should be noted that the London Borough of Camden partner has quit the project. This partner was piloting one of the use cases. Their specific analytics have been implemented in the remaining use cases in order to maintain the expected demonstrations.

2 MAGGIOLI USE CASE 1

2.1 DESCRIPTION

2.1.1 General Description

Use Case 1: Participatory policies against Radicalization

This use case will develop a collaborative data-driven analysis for the validation of existing policies to counter radicalization based on a participatory review of data coming from social media (e.g., Twitter, Reddit, RSS feeds) and open datasets (e.g., Global Terrorism Database (GTD) and RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism (RAND)). In addition, it will provide useful insights and valuable information to policy makers at any level (local, regional, and national) to update current policies and/or create new ones, while at the same time allow them to interact with other relevant stakeholders (i.e., LEAs, social services, schools, civil society) during the creation and modelling of new policies and specific countermeasures, ranging from early detection methodologies to techniques and policies for the monitoring and management of domestic radicalization.

2.1.2 Main Objectives

The use case objective is to improve operational efficiency, transparency, and decision making by using the PolicyCLOUD cloud-based platform. The PolicyCLOUD visualisation technologies will enable policy makers to identify issues, trends, and policy effects and interactions, while the analytics technologies will enable them to discover insights and find meaningful explanations about the effects of policies.

2.1.3 Use case's scenarios

Scenario A: Radicalization incidents	
Description	<p>Monitor the occurrence of radicalization incidents in the geographic proximity of a region.</p> <p>Data coming from the GTD and RAND will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the area of his/her interest and consult the different incidents that have taken place in a given period.</p>
Goals	<p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>

Scenario A: Radicalization incidents	
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	The present scenario will mainly help policymakers in the understanding the effectiveness of a given policy over time. If It gave the expected effects, our stakeholder will see a decrease of radicalized incidents over time. Also, the policymaker will have a clearer and more complete understanding of the radicalization situation in a given area.
Why: the user story	As a policy maker working in a major city, I am concerned about the possibility of radicalized groups attacking or spreading propaganda in my region. Having a clear tool with reliable data allow me to have a better understanding of the situation around me and how it changed in the past years, before and after important regulations were passed.

TABLE 1 – UC1 SCENARIO A

Scenario B: Radicalized groups and individuals	
Description	Identify the main actors (individuals or groups) involved in radicalised incidents or propaganda spreading through online and offline activities. Data from the GTD and RAND will be used. The Policy Maker can select a set of keywords in order to identify the individuals/groups active in the area of his/her interest and consult the different incidents that are linked to each of them.
Goals	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	This tool will allow policy makers to go in a specific case by case monitoring of groups or individuals spreading propaganda online. This will help in the identification not only of extremist recruiters, but also of keywords used in the first stages of radicalization.
Why: the user story	Not knowing what is the situation, is one of the biggest problems when we face radicalization, especially online. Widespread and well-organized groups need of course different actions if compared to a single radicalized individual. Having a tool allowing me to identify the different actors involved in this process and the material that they share online is fundamental for the work of a policy maker in the era of the internet.

TABLE 2 – UC1 SCENARIO B

Scenario C: Trend analysis	
Description	<p>Understand current and future trends of radicalization efforts through keywords detection, new entity recognition, and new terms identification.</p> <p>Data coming from the social media will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the keywords of his/her interest and consult the different information linked to them.</p>
Goals	<p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	<p>This scenario will support regulations and validation of policies regarding online propaganda, especially on social media. These media are knowingly difficult to regulate due to a lack of access or data.</p>
Why: the user story	<p>One of the major problems when dealing with online content, as a policy maker, is the absence of regulation. The internet is now part of everyone's life but we drastically lack laws about this subject, and online propaganda is spreading rapidly without effective tools to combat it. Thanks to this kind of tool, we will have the possibility to have a clearer view of what is happening online and try to regulate it in effective ways.</p>

TABLE 3 – UC1 SCENARIO C

Scenario D: (Near)real-time assessment of online propaganda	
Description	<p>Understand specific events and online activities (sentiment analysis, opinion mining, location surveillance, user monitoring)</p> <p>Data coming from the social media will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the keywords of his/her interest and consult the different information linked to them.</p>
Goals	<p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	<p>The online propaganda is a never-ending process in continuous evolution. Policy Makers need to have an instrument allowing them to control this process in near real-time in order to adapt policies and approaches to this issue and stop misleading propaganda and radicalization.</p>

Scenario D: (Near)real-time assessment of online propaganda

<p>Why: the user story</p>	<p>Radicalization is a process that needs to stop at the very beginning, otherwise we face the risk of a widespread phenomenon. Thanks to this tool, I have the possibility to monitor the online instances of keywords and groups having to do with the initial stages of political or religious radicalization. This is allowing me for a better understanding of the online propaganda machine and how to deal with it with new regulations.</p>
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TABLE 4 – UC1 SCENARIO D

2.1.4 Description of E2E scenarios

Before we describe in detail the end-to-end story for each scenario, it is worth mentioning there are some preliminary steps common to all the scenarios that need to be specified, as follows:

- a) First and foremost, the Policy Maker have to specify the domain: in this case is SECURITY.
- b) Then, he/she will need to provide a short description of the policy model and its main goals.
- c) Finally, the relevant stakeholders linked to the specific policy model will be specified (see Table 5 – Key actors for UC1).

In the following paragraphs, we describe the remaining steps to be followed by the Policy Maker for each of the defined scenarios.

Scenario A

- Policy Modelling Editor

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

1) Relevant KPIs:

- **UC1-KPI#7:** Number of identified occurrences of radicalization incidents in a given area
- In the properties of the KPI, the policy maker needs to specify the data source: **GTD** or **RAND**.

2) Name the selected Analytical tool:

- For the GDT
 - Type: Heatmap
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - “iyear”, the year when the incident occurred. The policy maker can select a unique value (type:EQUAL): 2017, or a set of values (type:GREATER_OR_EQUAL): 2017 [2017, 2018, 2019, 2020]

- “region”, the geographic area where the incident occurred. It can have a unique value (type:EQUAL): Italy, or a set of values (type:IN): 8 [Western Europe]
- For the RAND
 - Type: uniFrequencyDistribution
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - “start_date”, the date when the analysis starts. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 01-01-2017.
 - “end_date”, the date when the analysis ends. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 31-01-2017.
 - “variable1”, the column that will be considered in the analysis. In this case, the policy maker should specify MonthYear,
 - Type: uniGeographicalDistribution
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - “start_date”, the date when the analysis starts. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 01-01-2017.
 - “end_date”, the date when the analysis ends. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 31-01-2017.
 - “variable1”, the column that will be considered in the analysis. In this case, the policy maker should specify country,

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

- Policy Development Toolkit

The policy maker select the Policy Model defined previously and specify the relevant KPIs for its evaluation, in this case UC1-KPI#7.

Scenario B

- Policy Modelling Editor

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

1) Relevant KPIs:

- **UC1-KPI#8**: Number of identified active groups/individuals in a given area

- In the properties of the KPI, the policy maker needs to specify the data source: **GTD** or **RAND**.

2) Name the selected Analytical tool:

- For the GDT
 - Type: biAccumulatedDistribution
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - “start_date”, the date when the analysis starts. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 01-01-2017.
 - “end_date”, the date when the analysis ends. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 31-01-2017.
 - “variable1”, the column that will be considered in the analysis. In this case, the policy maker should specify summary,
- For the RAND
 - Type: biAccumulatedDistribution
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - “start_date”, the date when the analysis starts. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 01-01-2017.
 - “end_date”, the date when the analysis ends. The policy maker can select a date from the calendar view, e.g. 31-01-2017.
 - “variable1”, the column that will be considered in the analysis. In this case, the policy maker should specify event,

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

- Policy Development Toolkit

The policy maker will select the Policy Model defined previously and specify the relevant KPIs for its evaluation, in this case UC1-KPI#8.

Scenario C

- Policy Modelling Editor

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

1) Relevant KPIs:

- **UC1-KPI#9:** Number of new terms / keywords identified from the policy maker
- In the properties of the KPI, the policy maker needs to specify the data source: **Twitter**.

2) Name the selected Analytical tool:

- Entity detection
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - Initial keywords specified by the policy maker
- Data Visualisation
 - Type: Tag Cloud/Tables

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

- Policy Development Toolkit

The policy maker will select the Policy Model defined previously and specify the relevant KPIs for its evaluation, in this case UC1-KPI#9.

Scenario D

- Policy Modelling Editor

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

1) Relevant KPIs:

- **UC1-KPI#10:** Number of negative opinions on social networks from the different groups / individuals
- In the properties of the KPI, the policy maker needs to specify the data source: **Twitter**.

2) Name the selected Analytical tool:

- Sentiment analysis / Opinion Mining
 - Additional parameters to be specified:
 - Initial keywords specified by the policy maker
- Data Visualisation

- Type: Bar chart

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

- Policy Development Toolkit

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

2.1.5 Key Actors

The main actors involved in this Use Case are:

Role	Objective	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Maker¹	Prevention, De-Radicalization, Reintegration	Creation, modelling, experimentation, adaptation, optimization, validation of policies	Analytical, Screening Techniques
Local authority / Municipality	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Maintains informed about radicalization as a subject, Evidence based - healthy dose of scepticism
LEAs	Prevention	Training First Line Practitioners	Tempered and does not jump to conclusions
Policy Officers	Prevention	Experimentation and validation of policies	Ability to engage with people, Ability to build trust, Have empathy, Tempered and does not jump to conclusions, Effective initiator or partner in multi or inter-agency cooperation

¹ Entities that may create and apply policies related to radicalization management. Includes public authorities at central level (e.g. regions, ministries, EU), which have different rights and enforcement capabilities. They are the end users of the PDT.

Role	Objective	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Families	Reintegration	Educating Young People	Non-judgmental character
Teachers and educators	Prevention, Reintegration	Delivering Alternative Narratives	Willingness to spend time with young people, Ability to recognize/observe change, Intercultural understanding
Psychologist / school councillor	De-Radicalization, Reintegration	Family support	Ability to maintain relationship within a broad spectrum
Prison / Probation Practitioner	De-Radicalization,	Exit Strategy	Legal knowledge
Local community organizations and NGOs	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Ability to engage with people and build relationship, Speak the language of minority groups, Intercultural sensitivities
Religious leaders	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Ability to engage with people and build relationship, Speak the Language of minority groups
Journalists			Evidence based – healthy dose of scepticism

TABLE 5 – KEY ACTORS FOR UC1

2.2 KPIs

2.2.1 Business KPIs

Pilot business KPIs as defined in the Grant Agreement. New KPIs have been added following the stakeholders needs or request. These KPIs will be evaluated with feedback from the pilot policy-makers.

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI1
Title	Reduction of time to develop a (new) policy to counter radicalization targeting vulnerable groups (e.g., children, youth, migrant)
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>50%
Business Relation	Reduction of time and money spent by public authorities on the issues involved
Measurement Method	Feedback from the end users
Used for	Creation evidence-based policies

TABLE 6 – UC1 BUSINESS KPI1

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI2
Title	Increase stakeholders' engagement and multi-agent cooperation in policy development
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>20%
Business Relation	Reduction of time and money spent by public authorities on the issues involved
Measurement Method	Feedback from the end users
Used for	Creation evidence-based policies

TABLE 7 – UC1 BUSINESS KPI2

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI3
Title	Reduce time to make prediction of possible risk of radicalization
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>25%
Business Relation	Reduction of time and money spent by public authorities on the issues involved
Measurement Method	Feedback from the end users
Used for	

TABLE 8 – UC1 BUSINESS KPI3

2.2.2 Technical KPIs

Pilot technical KPIs as defined in the Grant Agreement. New KPIs have been added following the stakeholders needs or requests. These KPIs will be evaluated with feedback from the pilot policy-makers.

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI4
Title	Number of data sources integrated and linked in the PolicyCLOUD platform
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 3
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Giving end users access to more information coming from different sources

TABLE 9 – UC1 TECHNICAL KPI4

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI5
Title	Increased number of algorithms / analytics tools used by the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>20%
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform Feedback from the end users
Used for	Providing end users with tools allowing to have access to more data and analyse them more efficiently

TABLE 10 – UC1 TECHNICAL KPI5

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI6
Title	New tools for visualisation of radicalization efforts integrated and used by the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>=1
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform Feedback from the end users
Used for	Providing end users with tools allowing to visualize the results in a proper format

TABLE 11 – UC1 TECHNICAL KPI6

2.2.3 Scenario KPIs

KPIs defined for the Use Case scenarios.

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI7
Title	Number of identified occurrences of radicalization incidents in a given area
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 0
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Monitoring the radicalization incidents in a given region

TABLE 12 – UC1 SCENARIO KPI7

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI8
Title	Number of identified active groups/individuals in a given area
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 0
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Implement specific counter-measures

TABLE 13 – UC1 SCENARIO KPI8

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI9
Title	Number of new terms / keywords identified from the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 5
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Monitoring the data coming from social media and identify new radicalization trends

TABLE 14 – UC1 SCENARIO KPI9

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KPI10
Title	Number of negative opinions on social networks from the different groups / individuals
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 200
Business Relation	
Measurement Method	Data from PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Monitoring the data coming from social media and understand the sentiment of the active users

TABLE 15 – UC1 SCENARIO KPI10

2.3 USERS REQUIREMENTS

2.3.1 Business Requirements

Scenario	Businesss Requeriments
Scenario A: Radicalization incidents	<p>Policymakers are in constant need of well organized and reliable data. Thanks to this scenario, we are able to give to Regione Lombardia a tool according to the needs expressed. This tool will allow policymakers to monitor the situation of radicalization incidents in their region and to analyse it thanks to different filters and parameters. It will also allow to validate existing policies by monitoring the instances of radicalisation before and after the policy took effect.</p>
Scenario B: Radicalized groups and individuals	<p>This scenario will use public data in order to identify groups and individuals particularly responsible for radicalizations and propaganda both online and offline. It will also allow policymakers to identify keywords and situations to monitor with a particular focus. This scenario will also feed keywords and names of groups and individuals to Scenario C.</p>
Scenario C: Trend analysis	<p>Thanks to the output of Scenario C, policymakers will have an innovative tool to monitor social media for radicalization. Our stakeholders are concerned about the spreading of extreme political and religious ideas through media on which they have little to no control on. Thanks to this scenario, they will be able to identify clouds of keywords and monitor the evolution of the topic on social media.</p>
Scenario D: (Near)real-time assessment of online propaganda	<p>The Policy Maker can select the keywords of his/her interest and consult the different information linked to them on social media and online. This will allow for a near real-time assessment of the online instances of propaganda in various groups and social media that will enable the policy maker to have a much higher understanding of the situation.</p>

Table 16 – Business requirements

2.3.2 Visualizations Requirements

Feedback received during previous Co-Creation Workshops

- Many of the participants said they would like to see the integration of all scenarios running and have a demo account to play with the platform before they recommend any additional features to be added at this stage. This will be done during next co-creation workshop in May-June 2022.
- Include exporting capabilities of the evaluation reporting with the visualisations. This feedback has already been successfully addressed.

- Include the possibility to have more than one graph visualised per scenario in order to allow for comparative analysis of the results. This feedback has already been successfully addressed.
- Increase knowledge exchange between the public entities that are partners in the project and possible with other entities that would like to test it before they decide to acquire a license of use.

For UC1 “Participatory policies against radicalization” the visualization functionalities are very valuable as they enable the policy maker to check at a glance the results of the selected data and thus understand what is happening in an area of his/her interest. This instance is clearly underlined in the comments reported above. Hence, the first type of visualisation option to be included in the PDT shall be the heatmap. An example is provided in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 – EXAMPLE OF HEATMAP FOR UC1

For this specific scenario, data will be retrieved from the GTD and RAND, which are already available in a structured format. The policy maker shall be able to filter the data based on different criteria (e.g., location, date, number of incidents, attack type, etc.). Thus, the system should show the different panels based on the selected criteria.

In the same way, the panels must display the impact of terrorism for each criterion.

Number of terrorist attacks, 2017

FIGURE 2 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 3 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

Suicide attacks by target, male and female, Boko Haram, 2014–2018

Female suicide bombers were much more likely to attack public places.

FIGURE 4 – EXAMPLE OF PIE CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 5 – EXAMPLE OF STACKED AREA CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 6 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

Distribution of deaths by terrorism, 1998-2018

Terrorism has remained widespread even as total deaths have declined.

FIGURE 7 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 8 – EXAMPLE OF CHART FOR UC1

The opinion of citizens could be collected from their concerns expressed in social media. The events that have had the most impact (number of likes, comments, retweets) could be showed in different panels, with the timeline, the date, source and link to the original document source.

FIGURE 9 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 10 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

Additionally, the most important terms could be displayed using tag clouds, used to check the frequency of texts, using different sizes (bigger with higher frequency) and colours:

FIGURE 11 – EXAMPLE OF TAG CLOUD FOR UC1

TOP POST

A ver si nos aclaramos: -La comida ecológica NO es más sana -NO hace falta tomar chía, lino, açai o quinoa para comer sano -Comer sano NO es comprar pijadas en tiendas bio o macrobióticas -Comer verdura, fruta, legumbres o frutos secos Sí es sano. Da igual si son ecológicas o no
18/10/2018 twitter ↗

-Sí hay alimentos malos, cuyos efectos nocivos están probados. Ejemplo: muchos de los que produce CocaCola, empresa para la que trabajaba este señor. -Ojalá el ministro haga lo posible por frenar el consumo de basura comestible, que tanto daño hace a la salud de los españoles. <https://t.co/0fp9ABvUqo>
14/01/2020 twitter ↗

Si en tu confinamiento dominical no tienes muchas cosas en la nevera y quieres cocinar algo con ellas en lugar de pedir comida a domicilio, desde El Comidista podemos ayudarte: dínos de qué ingredientes dispones y te diremos qué puedes hacer con ellos. ¡Empezamos ya!
15/03/2020 twitter ↗

¿Cómo avanzaron los negros con los derechos civiles, las mujeres con el sufragio universal o los obreros con las condiciones dignas en las fábricas? Calladitos en sus casas desde la "no polémica". <https://t.co/KC8nxMvux4>
07/10/2018 twitter ↗

FIGURE 12 – EXAMPLE OF TOP POST OF TWITTER

In addition, it is also important to identify and take into account trends to predict possible risks and threats of radicalization. As an example, the Data Visualization Framework could display the information in the following way showing terms going up and down:

FIGURE 13 – EXAMPLE OF UI DASHBOARD TO EVALUATE TRENDS

Visualizations for UC1

Scenario	Visualizations
Scenario A.1	Heatmap (see Figure 1) Alternatively, a Bar Chart (see Figure 2)
Scenario B: Radicalized groups and individuals	Bar chart (see Figure 2) Alternatively, bar chart (Figure 7) Other type of chart (Figure 8)
Scenario C: Trend analysis	Dashboard (see Figure 13) + tag cloud (see Figure 11)
Scenario D: (Near)real-time assessment of online propaganda	Line chart (see Figure 9)

Table 17 – Visualizations for UC1

3 SARGA USE CASE 2

3.1 DESCRIPTION

3.1.1 General Description

Use Case 2: Intelligent policies for the development of agrifood industry.

The agri-food industry in the Aragon region has annual sales exceeding € 2.5 billion, represents 8.8% of production and 11.86% of employment in the industrial sector in Aragon. Globalization and the increasing complexity of markets pose a threat to all traditional industries.

This industry is formed for the most part by small producers and SMEs with little access to new technologies, which is why it is important to collaborate with the Government of Aragon for the implementation of new investment methodologies in diffusion based on artificial intelligence. At this time from Aragon we want to give a boost to this important industrial sector, important not only economically but also socially, since we must take into account that this industrial activity takes place in rural environments, and for a region so punished by depopulation, the agri-food sector is the best tool to settle the population.

3.1.2 Main Objectives

- Improve investments in agri-food promotion by the Government of Aragon.
- Facilitate tools and access to new technologies for small and medium producers, tools based on open data, social media analysis, opinion mining.
- Improve the distribution of products thanks to the tool created in the project, a tool that allows them to search and compare prices and their positioning of their products and their rivals.
- Support for decision-making in the investment of the different geographical areas with market study elements based on artificial intelligence.
- Bringing the agri-food industry closer to new technologies.
- To support policy makers in the design and modelling of new policies / updating existing ones.
- Create stable working groups between producers and policy makers that allow to improve both communication and the development of new tools.

3.1.3 Use case's scenarios

Scenario A.1: Politika price point	
Description	The policy maker defines the base case for wines X and Y as a set of parameters and their values. The base case reflects the current data for the two wines examined. Furthermore, the policy maker defines different alternatives in terms of a set of parameters and their values that are different from the ones in the base case and look promising in their potential for increasing the popularity of X.
Goals	The use case allows the policy maker to provide data for two competing wines, one from Aragon (e.g. X) and one from some other region (e.g. Y) that describe their current price, quality and advertisement effort. Policy maker can then support the wineries to define pricing alternatives and advertisement effort for Aragon wines to make those more popular among a specific population. Simulation results are visualized as charts that facilitate direct comparisons between the alternatives explored.
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	This tool allows knowing the motivation for buying Aragonese wines by analysing the optimal sale price and the analysis of the different parameters. This will allow us to help the wineries to establish an optimal price and promotional investment policy. This information will allow adjusting the promotional campaigns of the Government of Aragon in matters of promotion, the wine sector is strongly supported by the government of Aragon from two points of view, promotion through Sarga and export and marketing through Aragon Exterior
Why: the user story	Not knowing the price policy and the motivation to purchase the products of the competition is a handicap that we face when we define our investment policies in agri-food promotion. Likewise, knowing our optimal point of sale helps us to better define our promotion policies.

TABLE 18 – UC2 SCENARIO A.1

Scenario A.2: Price Evolution	
Description	Visualize the sale price of wine on the different specialized websites, with automatic warning systems that avoid penalties for contracts with large distributors.
Goals	Aragon wines and those from competition, supporting the improvement of commercial policy for the regional agrifood industry”
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	With this tool we can control prices for large retailers and avoid penalties for uncontrollable price drops. In agri-food promotion, contracts with large distributors are very important for the distribution of wine, a penalty for not controlling the price of other distributors, in addition to giving a very bad brand image, can lead to significant economic sanctions.
Why: the user story	The existence of a multitude of sales channels that are not controlled by the end user can lead to major economic problems for the end user, price control will allow us to establish commercial relationships with large distributors that are safer both from a commercial and economic point of view.

TABLE 19 – UC2 SCENARIO A.2

Scenario B: Opinion on social networks	
Description	Visualize the negative and positive opinions on social networks of the different products analysed allowing an automatic and immediate response to the end user.
Goals	Create an immediate communication with the end user, knowing their impressions, both positive and negative, that will allow us to interact with the end customer more directly.
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	Controlling the different opinions expressed on social networks about our products will allow us to adjust and increase the speed of decision-making in our agri-food promotion policies.
Why: the user story	In social networks we have a rapid definition of trends and opinions that are very important today. Traditional promotional media do not take into account the importance of the different social networks, in addition, the latter bring us closer to a younger public that is very important for the sector.

TABLE 20 – UC2 SCENARIO B

Scenario C: Trend Analysis	
Description	Analysis of the trends in the wine sector through the specialized websites of the sector.
Goals	This action will allow us to know the trends in each of the markets that are of interest, knowing the trends in the sector we will be able to adjust our diffusion policies taking into account all possible parameters.
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	Knowing the trends in the sector will allow us to adjust and increase our decision-making in our agri-food promotion policy.
Why: the user story	Trends in a market like wine are of vital importance to improve the promotion of products. Wine is a sector that largely moves by trends and fashions, detecting these in time gives you an important advantage over your competitors.

TABLE 21 – UC2 SCENARIO C

3.1.4 Description of E2E scenarios

In the next section we will analyse the different scenarios, starting from some common prescriptions such as

- a) First, the Policy Maker must specify the domain: in this case it is Analysis of trends and parameters for a correct distribution of public funds in promotion labours of the Aragonese wine sector.
- b) Then you will need to provide a short description of the main goals of the use case.
- c) Finally, the relevant actors linked to the use case will be specified (see Table 17).

The Scenario A.1 Politika price point pretends to find the correct price and marketing investment for one specific wine. We assume that price and quality are the main factors influencing consumers when purchasing wine. That said, consumers can also be influenced by their exposure to wine-related advertising/marketing campaigns and the wine preferences of their social circle.

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

KPIs:

- **KPI:** In this scenario the indicators are the number of wines used for analysing. It is difficult to identify, due to it is a proof of concept of the external integration.

Analytical tools:

- Data Visualisation- Visualization tools should be intuitive and at the same time informative. It is important that policy makers are able to efficiently assess data queries outcomes and impact, and to be able to connect deviation in results with alterations in inputs.
 - Type: scatter and ball to find the optimum ratio of price and marketing investment.

Additional parameters to be specified:

We define the following set of parameters of interest for estimating the **purchase motivation** for a particular brand of wine (e.g., X) in a specific region via **social simulation**:

1. Actual price for X
2. Quality (in a scale of 0 to 1) of X as determined by its average rating in a series of online reviews
3. Estimate of the average price of wines sold in the region of interest
4. Estimate of the maximum price for wine that is acceptable for an average consumer
5. Average quality of the wines sold in the region of interest (0 to 1)
6. Average income of the population in the region of interest
7. Maximum income of the population in the region of interest
8. Average relative exposure of individuals to the advertising campaign for X (0 to 1). We assume that average exposure is proportional to the relative size of the advertising budget for X compared to its competitors

We further assume that the population in the region of interest is represented as a social network, where each node corresponds to an individual. For each individual (e.g., A), each outgoing edge is labeled with a weight representing the influence (0 to 1) that A exerts on the wine purchasing decisions of one of its social connections. Each individual has a set of attributes that are relevant towards X. These include A's:

1. Income ranking (in a scale of 0 to 1) as determined by the ratio of its income to the maximum income for the region.
2. Sensitivity to the price of X as determined by the product of the difference of 1 minus A's income ranking times the ratio of the current price of X to the maximum wine price in the region. According to this estimate, poor individuals are more sensitive to the price of wines compared to wealthier ones.
3. Sensitivity to the quality of X as determined by the ratio of the current quality of X to the average quality of wines in the region, times A's income ranking. According to this estimate, wealthier individuals are more sensitive to the quality of wines than poor ones.
4. Susceptibility to the advertising/marketing campaign for X (0 to 1).
5. Susceptibility to social influence towards X (0 to 1)
6. Perceived influence for X from A's social circle. This is computed as the average purchase influence for X stemming from its social circle.

Based on these attributes, the model estimates A's **purchase motivation** for X as a linear combination of:

1. A's price sensitivity for X.
2. A's quality sensitivity for X.
3. The product of A's advertising susceptibility for X to the intensity of X's advertising campaign.
4. The perceived influence for X for A's social circle.

The simulations are executed by the Social Dynamics component of PolicyCLOUD.

The **Scenario A.2 Price Evolution** pretends to monitor the sale prices:

1. Monitoring the sales price of different wine references on specialized websites to generate alarm systems if prices fall below a minimum price
2. Benefit: avoid penalties in contracts with large distribution groups

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

Analytical tools:

- KPI 12 increment price in the last month Knowing price fluctuations is a very important indicator for wineries, trading companies and especially for establishing policies based on the prices of the sector.

Analytical tools:

Time evolution chart for the visualization of the price (see figure)

Additional parameters to be specified:

The analytical tool implemented in T4.3/T4.4 will manage just following parameters

- “start_date” and “end_date”
- “wines” : [a list of wines coming from the database*]

Max_number of wine to visualize

The **Scenario B Opinion on social networks** tries to identify negative and positive opinions that the customers and competitors have about different products (D.O, wineries, brands) gathered in Social networks.

All this information allows to:

1. Determine the impact of a campaign on consumers
2. Identify the profile of consumers based on demographic and social factors
3. Evaluate competitor’s strategies

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

KPIs:

- **KPI:** percentage of positive opinions versus negative ones in a time interval for one specific wine, brand, Denomination of origin

Analytical tools:

- Data Visualisation- Visualization tools should be intuitive and at the same time informative. It is important that policy makers are able to efficiently assess data queries outcomes and impact, and to be able to connect deviation in results with alterations in inputs
 - Type: Line Chart for the evolution opinion for the selected concept: Denomination of Origin, specific winery, specific brand, etc.

Additional parameters to be specified:

- “idate”, period of time to be evaluated.
- “region”, the geographic area of interest.
- “wine”, brand or Origin Denomination

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

The Scenario C Trend Analysis

Trend Analysis planned in T4.3/T4.4

1. Identification/extraction of already-known concepts related to the scenario world. An analysis needs to focus on the concepts that knit the words together to see the narrative, not just the word's frequency, for example: synonyms relationships, conceptualization through hypernym/hyponym, ontology-base conceptualization, or ontology-based topic modelling. These two last will be used as approaches in PC.

2. Definition what is trend: Those implicitly and explicit concepts which have changed the most with regards to the last period

For this scenario, the following parameters will be used:

KPIs:

- KPI 8 Total number occurrences. New concepts related to wine sector, that are trends in the source data
- KPI 9 relative Total n° occurrences %.

In this case, the analysis must add in addition to the sections and impact on social networks, the study of specialized websites, trendsetters and all the information available on the wine market.

Analytical tools:

- Data Visualisation- Visualization tools should be intuitive and at the same time informative. It is important that policy makers can efficiently assess data queries outcomes and impact, and to be able to connect deviation in results with alterations in inputs
 - Type: tag concepts, tables with more relevant concepts

Additional parameters to be specified:

Input parameters in the analytical tool developed in T4.3/T4.4:

- Start date
- End date

Category or individual (Filtering in the visualization). Pending to be discussed

- Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

3.1.5 Key Actors

The main actors involved in this Use Case are:

Actor	Role	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Maker	Coordinate investment policies in diffusion of the wine sector.	Coordinate different administrations with competences in the sector.	Analytical, Management.
Wine producers (wineries)	Provide information on the needs of the sector and the development of the tool.	Collect information necessary for the project.	Specification of the needs of the sector. Analysis of the actions carried out so far.
Designation of Origin	Group producers information.	Meeting with small producers	Analytical Coordination
Regional promotion agencies (Aragón exterior; Sarga ...)	Coordinate promotional actions.	Coordination meetings to learn about the promotional actions carried out both nationally and internationally.	Marketing. IT experience.
Agri food cluster	Support in workshops and information analysis.	Coordination meeting.	Marketing.

TABLE 22 – KEY ACTORS FOR UC2

3.2 KPIs

3.2.1 Business KPIs

Pilot business KPIs as defined in the Grant Agreement. New KPIs have been added and modified following the stakeholders needs or requests. These KPIs will be evaluated with feedback from the pilot policy-makers.

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI1
Title	Improve the impact of investment in agri-food promotion (wine sector)
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>5% sales
Business Relation	Improvement of the ratio of investment in advertising and sales
Measurement Method	% increase in total sales. Feedback form end users
Used for	Check the purchase motivation of the final buyer taking into account the parameters used in the politika tool

TABLE 23 – UC2 BUSINESS KPI1

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI2
Title	Coordinate actions of the different competent administrations
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>5% sales
Business Relation	Increase the profitability of investments in advertising by the competent administrations in the sector
Measurement Method	% increase in total sales
Used for	Make public investments in agri-food promotion more efficiently

TABLE 24 – UC2 BUSINESS KPI2

3.2.1 Technical KPIs

Pilot technical KPIs as defined in the Grant Agreement. New KPIs have been added and modified following the stakeholders needs or requests. These KPIs will be evaluated with feedback from the pilot policy-makers.

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI3
Title	Improve the flexibility of the data structure
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20%
Business Relation	Increase the impact of agri-food promotion through work with data and new technologies
Measurement Method	Increase data usage in %. Feedback form end users
Used for	Increase the efficiency of investments in promotion as well as the study of future actions based on data

TABLE 25 – UC2 TECHNICAL KPI3

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI4
Title	Provide real-time calculation capacity
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20% of the data
Business Relation	Through the different tools implemented in the project, I reduced the information analysis times for the execution of agri-food promotion policies.
Measurement Method	% data usage and time reduction in the final investment decision. Feedback form end users
Used for	The end user will be able to have a tool that reduces decision times in their promotional campaigns thanks to the use of the tools created for data processing

TABLE 26 – UC2 TECHNICAL KPI4

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI5
Title	Unification and/or interoperability of data sources
Priority	High

Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	10 data sources
Business Relation	Create stable databases that help increase sales thanks to investments in promotion
Measurement Method	Increase the number of databases related to the sector.
Used for	Have databases that offer us clear information both to the competent administrations and to the end user of the tools created

TABLE 27 – UC2 TECHNICAL KPI5

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI6
Title	Increase process speed
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>30% Reduce time
Business Relation	The reduction of decision-making times will lower the cost of promotion, making them more efficient at the same time.
Measurement Method	Checking the time reduction in making final decisions. Feedback form end users
Used for	Provide tools to the end user that favour and improve decision making

TABLE 28 – UC2 TECHNICAL KPI6

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI7
Title	Increase speed of information access
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>25% Reduce time
Business Relation	The reduction of decision-making times will lower the cost of promotion, making them more efficient at the same time.
Measurement Method	Feedback form end users Checking the time reduction in making final decisions.
Used for	Provide tools to the end user that favour and improve decision making

TABLE 29 – UC2 TECHNICAL KPI7

3.2.1 Scenario KPIs

KPIs defined for the Use Case scenarios.

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI8
Title	Total number occurrences
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>50%
Business Relation	Increase the number of impacts on networks that allow expanding the promotion of the product
Measurement Method	Calculate the increase in interactions in networks
Used for	Analyse the existing impacts and help increase the impacts generated

TABLE 30 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI8

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI9
Title	Relative Total n° occurrences %
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>10%
Business Relation	Increase the number of impacts on networks that allow expanding the promotion of the product
Measurement Method	Calculate the increase in interactions in networks
Used for	Analyse the existing impacts and help increase the impacts generated

TABLE 31 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI9

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI10
Title	Opinion (-1 (negative) to 1 (positive)) impact
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	Average positive

Business Relation	Control the opinions of the final consumer of the product seeking to increase the number of positive opinions
Measurement Method	Number of opinions analysed. Feedback for end users
Used for	Analyse the different opinions expressed about the product seeking to improve the trend of your products

TABLE 32 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI10

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI11
Title	Increment of the impact in the last month
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>15%
Business Relation	Being able to check the impacts of the different campaigns in a shorter time will allow us to implement corrective measures to the initial decision if necessary.
Measurement Method	% increase in impacts analysed
Used for	Analyse the impacts related to investments in promotion

TABLE 33 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI11

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI12
Title	Increment price in the last month
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	10% drop relative to dangerous price drops for the end user
Business Relation	Avoid sanctions in contracts with penalty clauses for selling below the price
Measurement Method	% price fluctuation
Used for	Check the sales of the different portals, final sales centers in order to provide the end user with their pricing strategy

TABLE 34 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI12

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KPI13
Title	Identify optimum price
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	2 wines has been optimised using Politika tool
Business Relation	Increase benefits
Measurement Method	Use of the platform
Used for	Identify the optimum price for the specific marketing investment

TABLE 35 – UC2 SCENARIO KPI13

3.3 USERS REQUIREMENTS

3.3.1 Business Requirements

Scenario	Businesss Requeriments
Scenario A.1 Politika price point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A detailed analysis of our products in relation to direct competition taking into account the different points of sale taking into account the following parameters: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A's price sensitivity for X. A's quality sensitivity for X. The product of A's advertising susceptibility for X to the intensity of X's advertising campaign. <p>The perceived influence for X for A's social circle</p>
Scenario A.2 Price Evolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A detailed analysis of the data will allow us to know the final sale price in the different channels, allowing us to apply the necessary corrective measures to avoid penalizing the end user.
Scenario B Opinion on social networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis, supplemented by predictive analytical functions A detailed analysis of the data extracted from social networks will allow us to improve the interaction with the end user and improve the analysis of purchase motivation through the analysis of the content of the opinions.

Scenario	Businesss Requeriments
Scenario C Trend Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data analysis, supplemented by predictive analytical functions • A detailed analysis of the specialized portals in the sector will allow us to detect market trends more quickly, which will allow us to focus promotional measures on these market trends.

TABLE 36 – BUSINESS REQUIREMENTS

3.3.2 Visualizations Requirements

Feedback received during previous-Co-Creation workshops:

Most participants agree that the main problems they face are lack of data, inaccurate data and lack of standards. This is a major barrier to implementing new policies in any field. In addition, data is decentralised and fragmented and very difficult to access. All this makes the quality of data very low and unreliable. Data are not always available in standard formats, nor are they centralised. It would be interesting to provide a single point of access to the data shared among all the entities that make use of it. Having the data represented graphically would help to better understand the information, analyse and process it and draw conclusions.

Many of the participants indicate that at this point it is very difficult for them to indicate how the platform could be improved. That said, several actions for improvement are proposed:

- Exporting results
- Being able to have more than one graph or type of graph per scenario to be able to compare information
- Customisable graphs

For the UC “Intelligent policies for the development of agrifood industry” the visualization dashboards are very valuable as policies try to boost the promotion of the regional wine sector by providing support and aid for investment in wineries and by promoting wines in third countries; therefore these policies seek to ensure that the efforts and public resources invested are reflected in the wine market, one of the most competitive and specialized at international level.

FIGURE 14 – POLITIKA PRICE RATIO BETWEEN WINES (ARAGON VS COMPETITOR)

FIGURE 15 – EXAMPLE OF UI WITH USEFUL CHARTS AND PANNELS FOR THE UC

For enabling policy makers to check in a glance the results of selected data analytics queries outcomes the following chart options with their associated data would be relevant for the use case. To collect the data and provide them from different perspectives, data sources can be filtered according to multiple criteria and show the different panels from several points of view. Thus, the data can be shown from several perspectives: distribution, competitors, customers, etc.

To identify the behaviour of the competitors and their strategies, both in sales and positioning, the data will come from the social networks probes that will be configured by indicating which competitors want to be considered and which will subsequently display the data under this competitive pursuit.

In the same way, the panels and dashboards have to display the impact of the campaigns on consumers. It may be useful to profile the type of consumer in order to try to determine whether

demographic and social factors are relevant to the perception of wine and its consumption habits. For this purpose, radar charts could be very useful as shown in the example:

FIGURE 16 – EXAMPLE OF CHART FOR CUSTOMER PROFILING

The opinion of customer could be collected from their opinions including panels and also the themes they mention. The documents of our customers that have had the most impact (number of likes, comments, retweets) could be showed in different document content panels, with the timeline, the date, source and link to the original document source. Additionally, the most important terms could be displayed using tag clouds, used to check the frequency of texts, using different sizes (bigger with higher frequency) and colors:

FIGURE 17 – TAG CLOUD REGARDING THE WORLD OF WINE

FIGURE 18 – EXAMPLE OF THE PANEL TOP POST

In accordance with scenario A, it is very important to know the variations in wine prices in order to plan an appropriate commercial offer as well as to avoid possible sanctions with distributors for penalties in the contract.

FIGURE 19 – EXAMPLE OF CHARTS TO CHECK THE EVOLUTION OF SENTIMENTS

In addition, it is also important to identify and take into account trends in the wine sector to determine the topics and terms and its evolution by comparing time periods. As an example, the Data Visualization Framework could display the information in the following way showing terms going up and down:

FIGURE 20 – EXAMPLE OF CHARTS TO EVALUATE SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

To evaluate the efficiency in the investment of public funds for wine promotion and the study of new positions among new consumers, it can be exploited the data which comes from the influencers with the most representative users and those who have more followers, as well as the specialized websites to determine if the campaigns are well received by these users/media.

Moreover, the opinion of these users and media is extremely relevant, so sentiment panels are necessary to collect their opinions and analyse the sentiment reflected in their comments.

The following figure could illustrate as a general UI interface how to display opinion and sentiment: This chart could be used to display in a functional way which is the average opinion about a theme. It shows in a glance if the sentiment is mostly positive or negative:

FIGURE 21 – EXAMPLE OF CHART TO ANALYZE THE TREND ANALYSIS BY TYPE OF WINE

This sentiment analysis could also be shown over the time using line charts. The example below can represent, for example, the behaviour of opinion or sentiment about a topic over the time:

To analyse the data, different charts and visualization options are defined to better evaluate the data to be displayed.

Scenario	Visualizations
Scenario A.1: Politika price point	Visualization of the optimal point for user engagement (figure14)
Scenario A.2: Visualize the sale price of wine on the different specialized websites	Visualization of the optimal point for user engagement (see Figure 14) Useful chart of price evolution (see figure 16) Bar Chart (see Figure 18)

Scenario	Visualizations
<p>Scenario B: Visualize the negative and positive opinions on social networks of the different products analysed allowing an automatic and immediate response to the end user.</p>	<p>Useful chart (see Figure 14) Display opinion and sentiments (see Figure 20) Chart opinion media (see Figure 21) Charts used for social media visualization (see Figure 22) Bar chart to analyse social (see Figure 23)</p>
<p>Scenario C: Analysis of the trends in the wine sector through the specialized websites of the sector.</p>	<p>Customer chart t (see Figure 15) Chart evaluate trends (see Figure 19) + tag cloud (see Figure 16) Panel top post (see Figure 17)</p>

TABLE 37 – VISUALIZATIONS FOR UC2

4 SOFIA USE CASE 3

4.1 DESCRIPTION

4.1.1 General Description

Use case 3 - Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis.

Sofia Municipality is constantly working to improve the urban environment and meet the challenges that the city is facing. Evidence-based policy making is crucial for addressing urban challenges in a cost-efficient way. The aim of this use case is to support Sofia Municipality's policy making in important areas of citizen's everyday lives by using crowdsourced data from its Contact Centre (CallSofia) as well as data from the air quality measurement stations, that are dispersed around the city.

The PolicyCLOUD project will support Sofia Municipality to improve its urban environment and address the challenges related to it through data assessment and validation. Furthermore, the city will be able to adapt the design of its policies considering analytics' results that combine information of sectors, related to 1) road infrastructure; 2) environment and air quality; 3) waste collection and waste disposal; 4) transport, and parking; 5) cleanliness of public spaces; 6) violation of public order, and other topics of importance to residents. Furthermore, the PolicyCLOUD tool will allow the city of Sofia to benefit from a trend and forecasting analysis and a cross-data analysis. By improving the policy making in the abovementioned areas, the quality of life for citizens will be enhanced, which is the overall goal of this project.

4.1.2 Main Objectives

- To support Sofia Municipality's urban policy making in key areas for the city.
- To support policy makers in the design and modelling of new policies/updating existing ones by enhancing their knowledge and capability to identify the problems, issues and trends related to the urban environment.
- To support policy makers in the adoption or modification of adequate policy making decisions on budget planning and effective use of budget and public resources.
- To enhance the Municipality's operational efficiency, transparency, and decision-making in order to improve the overall quality of life in Sofia.
- To utilize visualization to support policy makers to identify issues, trends and tendencies (incl. behavioural trends), and policy effects and interactions.
- To validate existing policies and assess potential policies and initiatives in focus areas.

- To facilitate more efficient use of resources.
- To share best practices and lessons learned with relevant stakeholders (at any level).
- To identify tendencies.
- To facilitate better control, monitoring and prevention.
- To create new ones based on the retrieved information.

4.1.3 Use case's scenarios

This Use Case will focus on 6 key areas of key importance to citizens and crucial for overall urban quality of life. All sectors that the Sofia Use Case will focus on will use data from Sofia Municipality's Contact Centre CallSofia (mobile application, 24/7 phone contact center, and web channel), with sector 2) Environment and air quality also using data from the air quality measurement stations in the city. Sectors 1), 3), 4), 5), 6) utilize data with similar attributes, variables and KPIs and will have similar end-to-end structure, while Sector 2) would add an additional type and source of data, and can include cross-analysis of data sources.

The sectors are as follows (and their number can potentially be increased in the future):

- 1) Road infrastructure, together with adjacent urban environment (such as pavement, fences etc.) is one of the most important and budget-consuming elements, that affects citizens' everyday life.
- 2) Air quality is also a key issue for citizens and priority for Sofia Municipality, which is dedicated to its long-term improvement, as well as the enhancement of the overall urban environment.
- 3) Waste collection and waste disposal is also an important area for the city, including efforts to provide more effective and efficient waste sorting and separate waste collection, more effective and sustainable overall waste processing and management, etc.
- 4) Transport and parking (incl. modernisation; ongoing improvement of service quality; more efficient and less time-consuming services for the citizens; etc.) alongside road infrastructure, are also among the key and most budget-consuming urban areas affecting citizens and focus of the Transport and Urban Mobility department of Sofia Municipality and the Urban Mobility Centre-Sofia.
- 5) Cleanliness of public spaces (incl. streets, parks, etc.) and 6) and
- 6) Violation of public order (in all degrees) is also among the issues of big importance for Sofia's residents.

Sofia's Scenarios

During the PolicyCLOUD project, Sofia Municipality will focus on the implementation of 3 scenarios. The goal of all these scenarios is to use the analytics and visualisations produced from the PolicyCLOUD platform to identify key information that could help determine policies and approaches to facilitate and encourage urban development and improved quality of life for Sofia's citizens.

- **SCENARIO A: VISUALISATION.** Sofia's first scenario will focus on the detailed and diverse visualisation of the data received with regards to the 6 abovementioned sectors.

- SCENARIO B: PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS. Sofia’s second scenario will provide a predictive analysis identifying trends and forecasts in the above domains to facilitate for better control and monitoring.
- SCENARIO C: ENVIRONMENT AND AIR QUALITY CROSS-ANALYSIS. Sofia’s third scenario (optional) will focus on the topic of environment and air quality and the cross-analysis between the data received from CallSofia and the data from the air quality sensors in the city.

The data from CallSofia, crowdsourced directly from citizens through their signals on non-urgent deviations in the urban environment and reported to Sofia’s Call Center either via the 24/7 telephone line, or the Call Sofia mobile app or via the desktop version of Call Sofia, allows policy-makers to get a detailed, up-to date information and snapshot of the types and geographical distribution of the urban challenges that the citizens are encountering every day, and to identify certain tendencies, In the same time, Call Sofia allows citizens to get directly and easily in contact with the Municipality, to signal issues, and to follow the process of their signals and the resolving of the issues on behalf of the City.

With regards to policy making, the three scenarios will support the local government policies related to the five key areas, will facilitate the improved long-term urban planning in Sofia and will allow for improved data-based policy making and the faster and improved implementation of new, more effective and efficient policies to solve the urban challenges of the city.

SCENARIO A: VISUALISATION	
Description	Visualise the signals received via Sofia’s Call Centre CallSofia related to 1) road infrastructure; 2) environment and air quality; 3) waste collection and waste disposal; 4) transport, and parking; 5) cleanliness of public spaces; 6) violation of public order. Provide a detailed analysis of their frequency over time and territorial distribution by categories / types, areas, districts, etc. to support and facilitate data-based municipal decision-making.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of long-term policy making in the 6 areas and overall urban planning and data-based policy-making in the city. • better envisioning and capacity building of district administrations and municipal administration in solving urban challenges. • assess and validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new ones based on the retrieved information. • use the visualizations as a tool supporting the development of more efficient policies and methods of tackling urban challenges. • facilitate better quality of urban services and overall urban capabilities and capacities. • facilitate more optimal resource allocation and control.

<p>Government policy and how this scenario supports it</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The City: the scenario will support the local government policies related to the six key areas, will facilitate the improved long-term urban planning in Sofia and will allow for improved data-based policy making and the faster and improved implementation of new, more effective and efficient policies to solve the urban challenges of the city. • The Citizens: more effective and efficient consideration and use of the data and feedback, provided by them, by the city. More effective and efficient policies resulting in problem solving and better, tangible effects for the citizens and the urban environment.
<p>Why: the user story</p>	<p>I, as a Policy Maker responsible for urban environment (road infrastructure; environment and air quality; waste collection and waste disposal; transport, and parking; cleanliness of public spaces; etc.) need to have better access to recent and historic data and data visualisations in order to develop more effective and efficient urban policies and guarantee ongoing improvement of the quality of life for the citizens.</p>

TABLE 38 – UC3 SCENARIO A

<p>SCENARIO B: PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS</p>	
<p>Description</p>	<p>Using predictive analysis to predict a future outcome.</p>
<p>Goals</p>	<p>The goal of this scenario is to use specially designed algorithms from PolicyCLOUD to predict future outcomes and trends with regards to the five abovementioned key sectors (potential challenges, effects of new policies, etc.) using the provided datasets.</p>
<p>Government policy and how this scenario supports it</p>	<p>This scenario will assist policy makers in creating effective policies that will address the development of the urban environment in the city and the ongoing process of providing improved quality of life for the citizens with regards to 1) road infrastructure; 2) environment and air quality; 3) waste collection and waste disposal; 4) transport, and parking; 5) cleanliness of public spaces; 6) violation of public order. With the use of the PolicyCLOUD platform, policy makers to be able to use statistics from predictive algorithms from the toolkit to assist them in making decision during policy creation process.</p>
<p>Why: the user story</p>	<p>I, as a Policy Maker, responsible for urban environment (road infrastructure; environment and air quality; waste collection and waste disposal; transport, and parking; cleanliness of public spaces; violation of public order, etc.) need to better access to recent and historic data and predictive capabilities to help me predict future outcomes and trends, thus facilitating my activities with regards to long-term urban planning and policy making.</p>

TABLE 39 – UC3 SCENARIO B

SCENARIO C: ENVIRONMENT AND AIR QUALITY CROSS-ANALYSYS	
Description	Provide a cross-analysis of the datasets on environment and air quality received via Sofia's call centre Call Sofia and the additional data provided by Sofia's air quality measurement stations to support and facilitate data-based municipal decisions in one of the key areas of urban development.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of long-term policy making in the area of air quality and, by extension, in other environmental areas related to air quality. • improved long-term health and quality of life of Sofia's citizens. • validation of existing policies; investigation if there is a need to update/modify them or create new ones based on the retrieved information.
Government policy and how this scenario supports it	The analytical functions of the PolicyCLOUD platform will provide an opportunity for a fuller distribution of the efforts of the teams from Sofia Municipality to work to improve the cleanliness of the air in the city, the results of measures taken to prevent pollution in specific areas and highlight when necessary. to step up work in another area.
Why: the user story	I, as a Policy Maker, responsible for the topic of environment and air quality, need to have better access to recent and historic data and information from different sources and the possibility to analyse it jointly and separately in order to develop more effective and efficient policies and guarantee ongoing improvement of the quality of air in the city.

TABLE 40 – UC3 SCENARIO C

In addition to the abovementioned goals, particularly with regards to the different sectors, with the help of the PolicyCLOUD platform and its visualization and prediction capacities, Sofia Municipality aims to achieve:

Sector	Goals
SECTOR1 - Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of long-term policy making in the area of road infrastructure (and adjacent infrastructure) • better envisioning and capacity building of district administrations and municipal administration in solving road infrastructure-related problems
SECTOR 2 – Environment and Air Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of long-term policy making in the area of air quality and, by extension, in other environmental areas related to air quality • improved long-term health and quality of life of Sofia's citizens • assessment of Municipal initiatives in the field
SECTOR 3 – Waste Collection and Waste Disposal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more efficient ways and methods of waste collection • improvement of long-term planning and policy making related to waste collection and waste disposal

Sector	Goals
SECTOR 4 – Transport and Parking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of the quality of the services • improvement of transport times and allowing better connections for citizens. • assessment of multimodal pricing schemes and initiatives such as “Green ticket”. • adoption of quantity measures for better parking management. • improvement of the overall parking capabilities.
SECTOR 5 – Cleanliness of Public Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of the overall level of cleanliness of public spaces. • improvement of planning and adoption and/or modification of current measures to ensure cleaner public spaces and the overall improvement of the urban environment.
SECTOR 6 – Violation of Public Order	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvement of long-term policies related to violation prevention and maintaining of public order.

TABLE 41 – UC3 SECTORS

4.1.4 Description of E2E scenarios

The Policy Model Editor (PME):

The Policy Model Editor (PME) is the core component which supports and guides the end-user to effectively create a Policy Model safely. More specifically, the PME is a Single Page Application that relays on the PDT backend REST API to fetch or store related entities of the Policy Model.

For all of Sofia’s scenarios, as they utilize data with similar attributes, variables and KPIs and will have similar end-to-end structure, the following parameters can be defined:

KPIs:

- # of incidents/signals
- # of incidents/signals per year
- # of incidents/signals per geographical location
- # of incidents/signals per category per location
- % per type of incident/signal
- % per month/signal
- % per year/signal
- change in frequency over the years

Configurable parameters related to the selected KPIs

- Dependant on choice - users should see either an Annual percentage increase/decrease in #
- Combined analysis including cross analysis of several criteria should be possible – e.g. per type and district and year

- Increase / decrease per type/ year/ district/ month
- Geographical spread per district/ per geo location
- Share of incidents per type / per month / per year

Once the policy maker has reviewed and submitted the Policy Model, he/she will be redirected to the PDT in order to evaluate the submitted Policy Model.

Policy Development Toolkit

For all suggested scenarios for UC3, the policy maker will need to select the Policy Model defined previously and specify the relevant KPIs for its evaluation. In the properties of the KPI, the policy maker needs to specify the necessary tools and parameters, so the toolkit can perform the analysis and show the corresponding visualization results for the Sofia Municipality.

4.1.5 Key Actors

The Sofia Use Case focuses on 6 key areas of importance to citizens. Therefore, the primary policy makers identified are part of Sofia Municipality's administration, working within units, responsible for the abovementioned focus areas.

Apart from Sofia Municipality's central administration, there are 24 district administrations, which are responsible for policy making on a district level. Sofia also has several organizations, which are governed by Sofia City Council and are responsible for strategy making and project development. Below is a list of responsible entities, concerning definition, implementation and monitoring of policies in the different sectors:

- **ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE AND URBAN ENVIRONMENT AND TRANSPORT AND PARKING:** directorate "Transport and Urban Mobility" within Sofia Municipality, representatives from the district authorities and Sofia Urban Mobility Centre, which is the municipal enterprise, responsible for mobility in Sofia.
- **AIR QUALITY:** directorate "Environment" and directorate "Climate, Energy and Air" within Sofia Municipality central administration, representatives from the district authorities and the Association for Development of Sofia, which is a non-government entity, established by the City Council.
- **WASTE COLLECTION:** directorate "Waste Management and Control Activities" within Sofia Municipality.
- **INNOVATION:** We're consulting with the "Digitalization, Innovation and Economic Development" department, responsible for implementation of digital and innovative solutions and improving the internal processes within the organization through innovation and SofiaPlan, responsible for coordination of the strategic and planning documents of Sofia. The activities of SofiaPlan are governed by Sofia City Council.

The main actors involved in this Use Case can be summarised as follows:

Actor	Role	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provide insights & information on the urban challenges faced by both citizens & policy makers -Provide information on and feedback regarding the modelling requirements and tools -Stay informed about the project's progress and, if necessary, participate in meetings related to it -Raise awareness about the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assist with the evaluation of the PDT and usefulness of the produced visualizations. - Participation and support in stakeholder workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical Policy creation process Management Municipal processes expertise Marketing
Local Municipality: experts from various Municipal departments, enterprises and projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provide information on the needs and the necessary KPIs -Provide information on urban challenges -Provide feedback regarding the modelling requirements and tools -Raise awareness about the project and the importance of data-based decision making for urban development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assist with the evaluation of the PDT and usefulness of the produced visualizations. -Participation and support in stakeholder workshops and /or internal meetings and information analysis -Support with wider community engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical Policy creation processes Municipal processes expertise Urban environment expertise Marketing
Data administrators: Sofia Municipality IT Department and Call Centre Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Provide datasets and additional information about the datasets - Provide feedback regarding the modelling requirements and tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assist with the evaluation of the PDT and usefulness of the produced visualizations -Verify the analytical statistics -Support in workshops and information analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical expertise IT experience. Analytical Municipal processes expertise

Actor	Role	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Local ecosystem: associations, clusters, NGOs, academic and R&D sector, local community organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Signals non-urgent deviations from normal practice within the urban environment -Provides feedback, ideas and suggestions related to the different aspects of the Project -Raises awareness about the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Support in workshops and information analysis -Facilitates community engagement and empowerment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical Technical experience Marketing Ideation Community engagement Hands-on experience and citizen perspective on urban environment
Local community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Signals non-urgent deviations from normal practice within the urban environment and gives feedback on urban challenges and opportunities, local community needs and existing policies -Raises awareness about the project 	Exact approaches to be defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical Hands-on experience regarding the urban environment and citizens needs Ideation

TABLE 42 – KEY ACTORS FOR UC3

4.2 KPIs

4.2.1 Business KPIs

The initial pilot Business KPIs, as defined in the PolicyCLOUD Grand Agreement section 1.3.3.3. were:

- Increase efficiency: Increased number/space for business, entertainment and health facilities >30%.
- Increase efficiency: Improve the success rate of new markets > 30%.

Due to the fact, that the initial topic and overall concept of Sofia’s pilot has changed during the project, the KPIs have been changed as well, with the support of both the Consortium and the pilot policy-makers, to reflect those changes.

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI1
Title	Increased efficiency: Reduction of time to develop a policy
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>50%

Business Relation	Increasing efficiency will lead to saved resources and time.
Measurement Method	Number of modified policies and new policies adopted in the 6 priority sectors per year.
Used for	Creation, adaptation and modification of policies

TABLE 43 – UC3 BUSINESS KPI1

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI2
Title	Increase in stakeholders' engagement in policy development
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>20%
Business Relation	Increasing the number and motivation of stakeholders for better policy development
Measurement Method	Feedback from stakeholders
Used for	Creation, adaptation and modification of policies

TABLE 44 – UC3 BUSINESS KPI2

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI3
Title	Policy recommendations implemented in the Annual city plans and key strategic documents related to the 6 priority sectors
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>25%
Business Relation	Improving the policymaking process
Measurement Method	Analysis of the annual city plans and strategic documents
Used for	Policy-making optimization and improvement

TABLE 45 – UC3 BUSINESS KPI3

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI4
Title	Increase in local ecosystem and community engagement and collaboration in urban policy development
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>15%
Business Relation	Improving the collaboration between citizens and the business environment
Measurement Method	Stakeholder feedback; CallSofia statistics; number of stakeholders involved in public consultations regarding new urban policies
Used for	Further involving stakeholders in the creation, adaptation and modification of policies; more effective and efficient co-created policy-making

TABLE 46 – UC3 BUSINESS KPI4

4.2.2 Technical KPIs

The initial pilot Technical KPIs, as defined in the PolicyCLOUD Grand Agreement section 1.3.3.3. were:

- Improve the flexibility of the data structure.
- Unification and / or interoperability of at least 8 different data sources.
- Increased process speed by 30%.
- Increased speed of access to information by 20%.

Due to the fact, that the initial topic and overall concept of Sofia’s pilot has changed during the project, the KPIs have been changed as well, with the support of both the Consortium and the pilot policy-makers, to reflect those changes.

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI5
Title	Number of data sources integrated and linked to the PDT
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>=2
Business Relation	Improving policymaking process in various domains of citizens everyday life (where datasets are available in the PDT)
Measurement Method	Datasets in PDT
Used for	Providing policymakers with more complete information

TABLE 47 – UC3 TECHNICAL KPI5

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KPI6
Title	Increased speed of access to information
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>15%
Business Relation	Helping policymakers have easier access to information
Measurement Method	Data from the PolicyCLOUD platform
Used for	Improved and faster policymaking

TABLE 48 – UC3 TECHNICAL KPI6

4.3 USERS REQUIREMENTS

4.3.1 Business Requirements

Scenario	Business Requirements
Scenario A: Visualisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A detailed analysis of the data, supported by accurate, diverse, user-friendly analytical graphs, which can be used for the urban planning, policy-making and more efficient and effective implementation of concrete activities in the 6 priority sectors, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ overall road infrastructure improvement ○ initiatives for improved air quality in different parts of the city ○ optimized waste collection and disposal processes ○ optimization of already implemented parking solutions and implementation of new ones ○ correct and accurate analyses for cleaner public spaces ○ encouraging citizens to provide the city with more information for better prevention activities • A set of good practices to use for the given sectors
Scenario B: Trend and forecasting analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data analysis, supplemented by predictive analytical functions. • Use of specially designed algorithms from PolicyCLOUD to predict future outcomes and trends with regards to the six abovementioned key sectors, using the provided datasets.

Scenario	Business Requirements
<p>Scenario C: Environment and air quality cross-analysis</p>	<p>In addition to the data analysis, visualization and predictive analytical functions mentioned above, this scenario will allow for the cross-analysis of the datasets received via Sofia’s call centre CallSofia and the additional data provided by Sofia’s air quality measurement stations. This will support and facilitate data-based municipal decisions in the field of environment and air quality - one of the key areas of urban development locally and globally, and will allow for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimized effort distribution within the Municipal teams • More efficient measures to prevent pollution in specific areas • Development of new solutions for tackling the challenges in the sector

TABLE 49 – BUSINESS REQUIREMENTS

4.3.2 Visualizations Requirements

The feedback from the participants of the two co-creation workshops is that a tool like PolicyCLOUD that facilitates data-based policy-making would be very useful for the activities of both Sofia Municipality and other cities around the world. As also mentioned in D6.14 USE CASES ADAPTATION & RECOMMENDATIONS [5], according to the participants, the provision of detailed data analysis, supported by accurate and diverse, user-friendly analytical graphs and predictive analytical functions will support the daily activities of the policy-makers and the different administrative departments, and in particular via:

- Visualising data according to the data chosen by policy maker, using filters and visualisations depending on the needs of the specific policy
- Providing the opportunity to synthesise the data, to compare them, separate different samples in a readable and visual format
- Providing a sufficient amount of objective information for the formation and prioritisation of policies.
- Providing accurate and up-to-date information and visualising information as a clear story behind the numbers
- Aggregation of data from different data sources.
- Predictive analysis

The comments were that the platform looks great, especially since it is still under development, and that upgrading it with additional data and capabilities for various visualisations and filters, as well as opportunity for different data breakdowns, and more interactivity with regards to user interaction and platform would be of added value.

The classification of the data by specific region, with analysis of the specific problems and frequency of reporting will enable the municipal and regional administrations to identify problems and trends in the specific region. The analysis will also facilitate the monitoring and control of the services under review,

allowing preventive action to be taken in case of identified potential risk and directing decision-making on policy adjustment and / or adoption, as well as on the effective use of the budget and public resources. Furthermore, thanks to visualization technologies, the effectiveness of the implemented policies can be monitored and if it is found that a measure does not work, it will be possible to change the actions taken.

For Sofia's use case, policy monitoring and analysis visualization tools have great importance. Analysing the data by category, type, territory and time will enable municipal and district administrations to identify problems, issues, and behaviour trends. The analysis will also facilitate monitoring and control of the services under review, enabling preventative action to be taken where potential risk is identified, and guiding decision making around policy adjustment and/or adoption and also around the effective use of budget and public resources.

Visualization tools should support decision-makers to obtain insights on the effects of introducing or changing policies. They should allow for data analytics, which will enable the authorities to understand the effects of the change and find explanations for the behaviours observed.

The PolicyCLOUD visualization technologies alongside the trend and forecasting analysis and cross-analysis capabilities of the tool, will also enable policy makers to identify tendencies. To analyse the data, different charts and visualization options are defined to better evaluate the data to be displayed.

It is key that visualization tools be both intuitive and informative, to allow policy-makers to efficiently assess data queries outcomes and impact, and to be able to connect deviation in results with alterations in inputs. It should be possible that data is shown by various criteria, including cross analysis between different data sets. The results will be presented to the policy maker using:

- **Line Graphs**, that illustrate the frequency of issues per area over time, etc.
- **Pie Charts**, that illustrate major categories of incidents
- **Heatmaps**, that illustrate:
 - the occurrence of incidents or issues, leading to citizen signals in a given area,
 - geographical distribution,
 - areas with repeating incidents over given time

Implemented visualisations 1: Heatmap

FIGURE 22 – HEATMAPS

Implemented visualisations 2: Pie Chart

FIGURE 23 – PIE CHART

Implemented visualisations 3: Bar Chart

FIGURE 24 – BAR CHART

Example 1: Dashboards

FIGURE 25 – DASHBOARDS SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.DECISIVEDATA.NET/](https://www.decisivedata.net/)

Example 2: Heatmaps

FIGURE 26 – HEATMAPS

Example 3: Circular Area charts

FIGURE 27 – CIRCULAR AREA CHARTS SOURCE: STACKOVERFLOW

Example 4: Line Graph

FIGURE 28 – LINE GRAPH SOURCE: RESEARCHGATE

Example 5: Charts, bars, tables with dynamic criteria (by type, KPI, location, etc.)

FIGURE 29 – CHARTS, BARS AND TABLES SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.DECISIVEDATA.NET/](https://www.decisivedata.net/)

Example 6: Pie Charts

FIGURE 30 – PIE CHARTS SOURCES: FHA, TEXASMUTUAL

When analysing the available data, various charts and visualization options have been defined in order to better evaluate the data to be displayed and to support more effectively and efficiently urban decision-makers. The visualizations mentioned and showcased above can all be applicable for all SOF scenarios, because, as already mentioned before, all of them will use data from Sofia Municipality's Contact Centre-CallSofia (with scenario 2) **Environment and air quality** also using data from the Airthings platform), utilizing data with similar attributes, variables and KPIs, and having similar end-to-end structure. Scenario 2) would add an additional type and source of data, can include cross-analysis of data sources, and also make use of all these visualisations.

Sectors	Visualisations
1 – Road Infrastructure 2 – Environment and Air Quality 3 – Waste Collection and Waste Disposal 4 – Transport and Parking 5 – Cleanliness of Public Spaces	All visualisations described above are applicable for all sectors, and can also be applicable for the predictive analysis.

TABLE 50 – VISUALIZATIONS FOR UC3

5 Conclusion

This report collects the final information on the fundamental aspects of the use cases and their development within the PolicyCLOUD project. Following a common methodology, end to end descriptions of the uses case's scenarios for the three project pilots, key actors and KPIs have been updated and reviewed. All the feedbacks collected in the co-creation workshops carried out by project partners have also been included.

Taking into account the opinion of the stakeholders and the technical evolution of the project, a complete review of all the requirements analysed in deliverables 6.3 and 6.10 has been included, completed with the contributions from both the co-creation workshops and the technical meetings held. carried out by the project resulting in an approximation to the final tools for the different use cases and us scenarios.

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